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THE REPRESENTING FORMULA OF $N(G, K)$

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, by combinatorial methods, the authors derive the representing formula between the number $N(G, k)$ of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factors with exactly k components and coefficients of the chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} , and the representing formula between the number $A(G)$ of all $S^{(n)}$ -factors and coefficients of the chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} , present classes of graphs $N(G, k)$ and $A(G)$, and give combinatorial identities related to $N(G, k)$. Finally, we solve the counting formula of K_d -factors in any complete d -partite graphs, the counting theorem of K_l -factors in any graph G without any K_{l+1} subgraph, the counting formula of the number of covers on shortest circles, as well as the explicit formula $\mu(K_n^d)$ of the mean color numbers of K_n^d .

1. Introduction

In this paper, we propose the concept of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factor. Recently, there are a number of necessary and sufficient conditions of 1-factor or (g, f) -factor. When $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 2 \leq i \leq 2\}$ (the number of K_2 is m), 1-factor (or perfect matching) is a special case of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factor. $S^{(n)}$ -factors are different from (g, f) -factors, contents of two definitions are indistinguished. When $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : k \leq i \leq k\}$ (the number of K_k is m , and $km = n$), K_k -factor is a special case of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factor. In [10], E. J. Farrell and J. M. Guo discussed the characterizing of matching polynomials (or 1-factors). In [13], M. N. Ellingham, Yunsun Nam, Heinz-Jürgen Voss presented connected (g, f) -factors. In [14], Potra Johann derived the structure of graphs with a unique k -factor. In [15], Atsushi Kaneko gained a necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a path factor. The lectures of 1-factors or (g, f) -factors have been belonged to the field of existences, here for us, we consider principally enumeration of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factors, our methods are from combinatorial idea such as recurrence relations or inverse problems. We research the significance of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factors as follows: 1. enumeration of graph theory; 2. combinatorial values (main combinatorial identities); 3. computer and code (regular- m -furcating tree, special regular 2-furcating tree); 4. other aspects. (the mean colour numbers $\mu(G)$, we complete these papers, see LiMin Yang and TianMing Wang [16] and [17].)

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Definition 1.1. Let $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$, $n \geq 1$, and K_i is a complete graph with i vertices, if M is a subgraph of a graph G , and any component of M is isomorphic to some element of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$, then M is called one $S^{(n)}$ -subgraph, if M is a spanning subgraph of the graph G , then M is called one $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factor .

Definition 1.2. If M is a spanning subgraph of the graph G , each component of M is all isomorphic to K_k , then M is called one K_k -factor.

Complexity: It is easy to see that $I(G, x)$ is NP-hard to compute.(see [1])

Let $N(G, k)$ denote the number of $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factors with exactly k components, $A(G)$ is the number of all $S^{(n)} = \{K_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ -factors, namely, $A(G) = \sum_{k=1}^n N(G, k)$. In [1], by partition-map-relation, the authors obtained the counting formula of $N(K_n, k)$. In [2], in the use of combinatorial convolutions, the authors derived the counting formula of $A(K_n)$. In [3], the author has found myself the recurrence relation by covering methods, and gained the formula of $A(0 \odot C_n)$. In [4], we proved the recurrence formula of $S^{(n)}$ -factors of regular m -furcating tree by analyzing the relation among m , i and t . They have been very difficult problems and heat contents that we count $N(G, k)$ and $A(G)$. In this paper, by combinatorial methods, the authors solve the representing formula between $N(G, k)$ and coefficients of the chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} , and the representing formula between $A(G)$ and coefficients of the chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} , present the counting formulas of classes of graphs $N(G, k)$ and $A(G)$, and some combinatorial identities on $N(G, k)$ are given. Finally, we solve the very difficult and heat problem on the the counting formula of K_d -factors in any complete d -partite $G = K_{n, n, \dots, n}$, the counting formula of the number of covers on shortest circles, as well as the explicit formula $\mu(K_n^d)$ of the mean numbers of K_n^d .

2. Basic Lemmas

Here we will denote that $\alpha(G, k)$ is the number of partitions of $V(G)$ into exactly k non-empty independent sets of any graph G .

Lemma 2.1 ([1]). *Let K_n be a complete graph with n vertices. Then the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly k components in K_n :*

$$N(K_n, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^n ib_i = n, \\ \sum_{i=1}^n b_i = k}} \frac{n!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i! (i!)^{b_i}} .$$

Lemma 2.2 ([1]). *Suppose K_n is a complete graph with n vertices, then the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors in K_n :*

$$A(K_n) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^n}{k!} .$$

Lemma 2.3 ([5]). *If $s(n, k)$ is the Stirling number of the first kind, $S(n, k)$ is the Stirling number of the second kind, then $[s(n, k)] = [S(n, k)]^{-1}$, where*

$$[s(n, k)] = \begin{pmatrix} s(1, 1) & s(1, 2) & \cdots & s(1, n) \\ s(2, 1) & s(2, 2) & \cdots & s(2, n) \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ s(n-1, 1) & s(n-1, 2) & \cdots & s(n-1, n) \\ s(n, 1) & s(n, 2) & \cdots & s(n, n) \end{pmatrix}_{n \times n},$$

$$[S(n, k)] = \begin{pmatrix} S(1, 1) & S(1, 2) & \cdots & S(1, n) \\ S(2, 1) & S(2, 2) & \cdots & S(2, n) \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ S(n-1, 1) & S(n-1, 2) & \cdots & S(n-1, n) \\ S(n, 1) & S(n, 2) & \cdots & S(n, n) \end{pmatrix}_{n \times n}.$$

Lemma 2.4 ([5]). *If $S(n, k)$ is the Stirling number of the second kind, then*

$$N(K_n, k) = S(n, k).$$

Lemma 2.5 ([7]). *Suppose \bar{G} is a complementary graph of G , then the chromatic polynomial of G is as the following*

$$f(G, t) = \sum_{r=1}^n \left[\sum_{k=1}^n N(\bar{G}, k) s(k, r) \right] t^r,$$

where $N(\bar{G}, k)$ denotes the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly k components in \bar{G} .

Lemma 2.6. *Suppose G is not an empty graph, then*

$$\sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n N(\bar{G}, k) s(k, r) = 0.$$

Proof. The result follows from $f(G, 1) = \sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n N(\bar{G}, k) s(k, r)$ and $f(G, 1) = 0$. \square

3. The representing formula of $N(G, k)$

In this section, our main result is the representing formula of $N(G, k)$ as follows.

Theorem 3.1. *If G is a graph with n vertices, and the chromatic polynomial of the complementary graph \bar{G} of G is $f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{p=1}^n Y_p t^p$, then the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly k components is the following*

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n N(K_p, k) Y_p,$$

where

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p i b_i = p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i = k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i! (i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 1 \leq p \leq n, \quad 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

Proof. By combinatorial and algebraic methods, we will prove the theorem. By lemma 2.5, we have the chromatic polynomial of \bar{G}

$$f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{r=1}^n \left[\sum_{k=1}^n N(G, k) s(k, r) \right] t^r$$

and

$$f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{p=1}^n Y_p t^p,$$

so that we have the equal systems

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{k=1}^n N(G, k) s(k, 1) = Y_1, \\ \sum_{k=1}^n N(G, k) s(k, 2) = Y_2, \\ \dots \dots \\ \sum_{k=1}^n N(G, k) s(k, n) = Y_n, \end{cases}$$

(3.1)

$$\begin{cases} s(1, 1)N(G, 1) + s(2, 1)N(G, 2) + \dots + s(n, 1)N(G, n) = Y_1, \\ s(1, 2)N(G, 1) + s(2, 2)N(G, 2) + \dots + s(n, 2)N(G, n) = Y_2, \\ \dots \dots \dots \\ s(1, n-1)N(G, 1) + s(2, n-1)N(G, 2) + \dots + s(n, n-1)N(G, n) = Y_{n-1}, \\ s(1, n)N(G, 1) + s(2, n)N(G, 2) + \dots + s(n, n)N(G, n) = Y_n, \end{cases}$$

(3.2)

By Lemma 2.3, we have $[s(n, k)] = [S(n, k)]^{-1}$ (Inverse relations derived by combinatorial idea, see [5]).

$$[s(n, k)][S(n, k)] = E, \quad [S(n, k)]'[s(n, k)]' = E$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} S(1, 1) & S(2, 1) & \dots & S(n-1, 1) & S(n, 1) \\ S(1, 2) & S(2, 2) & \dots & S(n-1, 2) & S(n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ S(1, n) & S(2, n) & \dots & S(n-1, n) & S(n, n) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} s(1, 1) & s(2, 1) & \dots & s(n-1, 1) & s(n, 1) \\ s(1, 2) & s(2, 2) & \dots & s(n-1, 2) & s(n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ s(1, n) & s(2, n) & \dots & s(n-1, n) & s(n, n) \end{pmatrix} = E \\ & \begin{pmatrix} s(1, 1) & s(2, 1) & \dots & s(n-1, 1) & s(n, 1) \\ s(1, 2) & s(2, 2) & \dots & s(n-1, 2) & s(n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ s(1, n) & s(2, n) & \dots & s(n-1, n) & s(n, n) \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} S(1, 1) & S(2, 1) & \dots & S(n-1, 1) & S(n, 1) \\ S(1, 2) & S(2, 2) & \dots & S(n-1, 2) & S(n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ S(1, n) & S(2, n) & \dots & S(n-1, n) & S(n, n) \end{pmatrix} \\ & \hspace{15em} (3.3) \end{aligned}$$

By (3.2), we have the equality

$$\begin{pmatrix} N(G, 1) \\ N(G, 2) \\ \dots \\ N(G, n-1) \\ N(G, n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} s(1, 1) & s(2, 1) & \dots & s(n, 1) \\ s(1, 2) & s(2, 2) & \dots & s(n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ s(1, n-1) & s(2, n-1) & \dots & s(n, n-1) \\ s(1, n) & s(2, n) & \dots & s(n, n) \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ \dots \\ Y_{n-1} \\ Y_n \end{pmatrix}$$

By (3.3), there is the equal n -tuples

$$\begin{pmatrix} N(G, 1) \\ N(G, 2) \\ \dots \\ N(G, n-1) \\ N(G, n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} S(1, 1) & S(2, 1) & \dots & S(n, 1) \\ S(1, 2) & S(2, 2) & \dots & S(n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ S(1, n-1) & S(2, n-1) & \dots & S(n, n-1) \\ S(1, n) & S(2, n) & \dots & S(n, n) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ \dots \\ Y_{n-1} \\ Y_n \end{pmatrix}$$

By Lemma 2.4, there is the formula $S(n, k) = N(K_n, k)$. Then

$$\begin{pmatrix} N(G, 1) \\ N(G, 2) \\ \dots \\ N(G, n-1) \\ N(G, n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N(K_1, 1) & N(K_2, 1) & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, 1) & N(K_n, 1) \\ N(K_1, 2) & N(K_2, 2) & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, 2) & N(K_n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ N(K_1, n-1) & N(K_2, n-1) & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, n-1) & N(K_n, n-1) \\ N(K_1, n) & N(K_2, n) & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, n) & N(K_n, n) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ \dots \\ Y_{n-1} \\ Y_n \end{pmatrix}$$

When $k > n$, $N(K_n, k) = 0$, then there is the equality

$$\begin{pmatrix} N(G, 1) \\ N(G, 2) \\ \dots \\ N(G, n-1) \\ N(G, n) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N(K_1, 1) & N(K_2, 1) & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, 1) & N(K_n, 1) \\ 0 & N(K_2, 2) & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, 2) & N(K_n, 2) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & N(K_{n-1}, n-1) & N(K_n, n-1) \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & N(K_n, n) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ \dots \\ Y_{n-1} \\ Y_n \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.4)$$

so the representing formula of $N(G, k)$ is derived from (3.4)

$$N(G, k) = N(K_k, k)Y_k + N(K_{k+1}, k)Y_{k+1} + \dots + N(K_{n-1}, k)Y_{n-1} + N(K_n, k)Y_n,$$

for $1 \leq k \leq n$. Namely, $N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n N(K_p, k)Y_p$, where Y_p ($1 \leq p \leq n$) are coefficients of the chromatic polynomial $f(\bar{G}, t)$ and

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p ib_i=p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i=k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i!(i!)^{b_i}}$$

(obtained by Lemma 2.1) here $1 \leq p \leq n$, $1 \leq k \leq n$. \square

4. The representing formula of $A(G)$

In the segment, we characterize the representing formula of $A(G)$.

Theorem 4.1. *If G is the graph with n vertices, and the chromatic polynomial of the complementary graph \bar{G} of G is $f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{p=1}^n Y_p t^p$, then the number of all $S^{(n)}$ -factors in G is the following*

$$A(G) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!} Y_p.$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.1, there are equalities:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} N(G, 1) = N(K_1, 1)Y_1 + N(K_2, 1)Y_2 + \cdots + N(K_{n-1}, 1)Y_{n-1} + N(K_n, 1)Y_n, \\ N(G, 2) = N(K_2, 2)Y_2 + \cdots + N(K_{n-1}, 2)Y_{n-1} + N(K_n, 2)Y_n, \\ \cdots \quad \cdots \quad \cdots \quad \cdots \quad \cdots \\ N(G, n-1) = N(K_{n-1}, n-1)Y_{n-1} + N(K_n, n-1)Y_n, \\ N(G, n) = N(K_n, n)Y_n, \end{array} \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned} A(G) &= \sum_{k=1}^n N(G, k) \\ &= N(K_1, 1)Y_1 + [N(K_2, 1) + N(K_2, 2)]Y_2 + \cdots \\ &\quad + [N(K_{n-1}, 1) + N(K_{n-1}, 2) + \cdots + N(K_{n-1}, n-1)]Y_{n-1} \\ &\quad + [N(K_n, 1) + N(K_n, 2) + \cdots + N(K_n, n-1) + N(K_n, n)]Y_n \\ &= A(K_1)Y_1 + A(K_2)Y_2 + \cdots + A(K_{n-1})Y_{n-1} + A(K_n)Y_n \\ &= \sum_{p=1}^n A(K_p)Y_p, \end{aligned}$$

where $A(K_p) = \sum_{k=1}^p N(K_p, k)$, for $1 \leq p \leq n$.

By Lemma 2.2,

$$A(K_p) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!}, \quad 1 \leq p \leq n.$$

Then

$$A(G) = \sum_{p=1}^n \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!} Y_p = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!} Y_p,$$

where Y_p ($1 \leq p \leq n$) are coefficients of the chromatic polynomial $f(\bar{G}, t)$. \square

5. Nnumeration of classes of graphs

In the section, we present classes of graphs $N(G, k)$ and $A(G)$. Specially, enumeration of complementary trees is solved.

Theorem 5.1. *Suppose G is a $(n-2)$ -regular graph with n (even $2m$) vertices, then the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly k components is the following*

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n N(K_p, k)Y_p,$$

where for $1 \leq p \leq m-1$, $Y_p = 0$, for $m \leq p \leq 2m$, $Y_p = (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p}$,

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p ib_i=p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i=k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i!(i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 1 \leq p, k \leq n.$$

Proof. Because G is a $(n-2)$ -regular graph, \bar{G} is 1-regular graph, including the number m of K_2 , then $\bar{G} = K_2 \cup K_2 \cup \cdots \cup K_2$.

The chromatic polynomial of the complementary graph \bar{G} is as follows

$$\begin{aligned} f(\bar{G}, t) &= f(K_2, t)f(K_2, t) \cdots f(K_2, t) = f^m(K_2, t) = t^m(t-1)^m \\ &= t^m \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^{m-i} \binom{m}{i} t^i = \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^{m-i} \binom{m}{i} t^{m+i} \\ &= \sum_{p=m}^{2m} (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p} t^p, \end{aligned}$$

$$Y_p = 0, \quad 1 \leq p \leq m-1; \quad Y_p = (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p}, \quad m \leq p \leq 2m.$$

By Theorem 3.1, we have the equality

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n N(K_p, k) Y_p,$$

where for $1 \leq p \leq m-1$, $Y_p = 0$, for $m \leq p \leq 2m$, $Y_p = (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p}$,

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{p \\ \sum_{i=1}^p i b_i = p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i = k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i! (i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 1 \leq p, \quad k \leq n.$$

□

Theorem 5.2. Suppose G is a $(n-2)$ -regular graph with n (even $2m$) vertices, then

$$A(G) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=m}^{2m} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p} \frac{k^p}{k!}.$$

Proof. By Theorem 4.1 $A(G) = \sum_{p=1}^n A(K_p) Y_p$, and by Theorem 5.1, when $1 \leq p \leq m-1$, $Y_p = 0$, when $m \leq p \leq n = 2m$, $Y_p = (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p}$, finally, there is the equality

$$A(G) = \sum_{p=m}^{2m} (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p} A(K_p),$$

and by Lemma 2.2 $A(K_p) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!}$, for $m \leq p \leq n$. So we have the formula

$$A(G) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=m}^{2m} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{2m-p} \binom{m}{2m-p} \frac{k^p}{k!}.$$

□

Theorem 5.3. *Suppose G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph with n vertices, $n \geq 6$ and $\bar{G} \cong C_n$, then*

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} N(K_p, k),$$

where

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p ib_i=p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i=k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i!(i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 2 \leq p, k \leq n.$$

Proof. If G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph, then \bar{G} is a 2-regular graph with n vertices, and $\bar{G} \cong C_n$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(\bar{G}, t) &= f(C_n, t) = (t-1)^n + (-1)^n(t-1) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} \binom{n}{k} t^k + (-1)^n(t-1) \\ &= [(-1)^{n-1} \binom{n}{1} + (-1)^n]t + (-1)^{n-2} \binom{n}{2} t^2 \\ &\quad + \cdots + (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} t^p + \cdots + (-1)^1 \binom{n}{n-1} t^{n-1} + t^n, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= (-1)^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{1}, Y_2 = (-1)^{n-2} \binom{n}{2}, Y_3 = (-1)^{n-3} \binom{n}{3}, \\ &\cdots, Y_p = (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p}, \cdots, Y_{n-1} = -\binom{n}{n-1}, Y_n = 1. \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 3.1, then $N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n N(K_p, k) Y_p$. For $k=1$, G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph, $G \neq K_n$, then $N(G, 1) = 0$; For $2 \leq k \leq n$,

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} N(K_p, k),$$

where

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p ib_i=p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i=k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i!(i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 2 \leq p, k \leq n.$$

Note Suppose G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph, $\bar{G} = C_{i_1} \cup C_{i_2} \cup \cdots \cup C_{i_m}$, $i_1 + i_2 + \cdots + i_m = n$, analogous to Theorem 5.3, we would have the corresponding result. \square

Theorem 5.4. *Suppose G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph with n vertices, $n \geq 6$ and $\bar{G} \cong C_n$, then*

$$A(G) = (-1)^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{1} + \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=2}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} \frac{k^p}{k!}.$$

Proof. Because G is a $(n-3)$ -regular graph, $\bar{G} \cong C_n$ and by Theorem 5.3, then

$$\begin{aligned} f(\bar{G}, t) &= f(C_n, t) \\ &= (-1)^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{1} t + (-1)^{n-2} \binom{n}{2} t^2 + \cdots + (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} t^p \\ &\quad + \cdots + (-1) \binom{n}{1} t^{n-1} + t^n, \end{aligned}$$

$$Y_1 = (-1)^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{1}, Y_2 = (-1)^{n-2} \binom{n}{2}, \dots,$$

$$Y_p = (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p}, \dots, Y_{n-1} = (-1) \binom{n}{1}, Y_n = 1.$$

By Theorem 4.1, we have

$$A(G) = \sum_{p=1}^n A(K_p) Y_p = (-1)^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{1} + \sum_{p=2}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} A(K_p),$$

and by Lemma 2.2

$$A(K_p) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!}, \quad 2 \leq p \leq n,$$

finally

$$A(G) = (-1)^{n-1} \binom{n-1}{1} + \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=2}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n}{p} \frac{k^p}{k!}.$$

Note Let G be a $(n-3)$ -regular graph, $\bar{G} = C_{i_1} \cup C_{i_2} \cup \cdots \cup C_{i_m}$, $i_1 + i_2 + \cdots + i_m = n$, we would also have the corresponding result. \square

Theorem 5.5. *If T is a tree with n vertices, and \bar{T} is a complementary complementary graph of T , then*

$$N(\bar{T}, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} N(K_p, k),$$

where

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p i b_i = p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i = k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i! (i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 2 \leq p, k \leq n.$$

Proof. Let G be a tree with n vertices. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(T, t) &= t(t-1)^{n-1} = t \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-1-k} \binom{n-1}{k} t^k \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-1-k} \binom{n-1}{k} t^{k+1} \\
 &= (-1)^{n-1} t + (-1)^{n-2} \binom{n-1}{1} t^2 + (-1)^{n-3} \binom{n-1}{2} t^3 + \cdots \\
 &\quad + (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} t^p + \cdots + (-1) \binom{n-1}{n-2} t^{n-1} + t^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

When $1 \leq p \leq n$, $Y_p = (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1}$. By Theorem 3.1 $N(\bar{T}, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n N(K_p, k) Y_p$. Then

$$N(\bar{T}, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} N(K_p, k),$$

where

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p i b_i = p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i = k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i! (i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 2 \leq p, k \leq n.$$

□

Theorem 5.6. *If T is a tree with n vertices, and \bar{T} is a complementary graph of T , then*

$$A(\bar{T}) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} \frac{k^p}{k!}.$$

Proof. By Theorem 5.5,

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(T, t) &= (-1)^{n-1} t + (-1)^{n-2} \binom{n-1}{1} t^2 + \cdots + (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} t^p \\
 &\quad + \cdots + (-1) \binom{n-1}{n-2} t^{n-1} + t^n,
 \end{aligned}$$

then

$$Y_p = (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1}, \quad 1 \leq p \leq n.$$

By Theorem 4.1,

$$A(\bar{T}) = \sum_{p=1}^n A(K_p) Y_p = \sum_{p=1}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} A(K_p),$$

and

$$A(K_p) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!}, \quad 1 \leq p \leq n,$$

so we derive the formula

$$A(\bar{T}) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} \frac{k^p}{k!}.$$

Here we solve the explicit formula of any complementary tree \bar{T} on enumeration of $S^{(n)}$ -factors. \square

Theorem 5.7. *If G is a windgraph K_n^d , K_1 is a meet vertex of K_n with the number d , (or K_1 is a intersection vertex of the number d K_n), then*

$$N(K_n^d, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{d(n-1)+1} N(K_p, k) Y_p,$$

where

$$Y_1 = 0, \quad Y_p = \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} S(n, l_1) \cdots S(n, l_d) \right] s(k, p-1)$$

for $2 \leq p \leq d(n-1) + 1$.

Proof. Let G be K_n^d . Then $\bar{G} = K_1 \cup H$, H is a complete complete d -partite graph, thus assume that $H = K_{n-1, n-1, \dots, n-1}$ with the number d of $n-1$, say.

$$\begin{aligned} N(\bar{H}, k) &= \sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} N(K_{n-1}, l_1) N(K_{n-1}, l_2) \cdots N(K_{n-1}, l_d) \\ &= \sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} S(n-1, l_1) S(n-1, l_2) \cdots S(n-1, l_d). \end{aligned}$$

The chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} is as follows

$$f(\bar{G}, t) = f(K_1 \cup H, t) = f(K_1, t) f(H, t) = t f(H, t).$$

By Lemma 2.5, then we obtain the chromatic polynomial $f(\bar{G}, t)$,

$$\begin{aligned} f(\bar{G}, t) &= t \sum_{r=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} N(\bar{H}, k) s(k, r) \right] t^r \\ &= t \sum_{r=1}^{d(n-1)} \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, r) t^r \\ &= \sum_{r=1}^{d(n-1)} \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, r) t^{r+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Coefficients of $f(\bar{G}, t)$ are the following

$$Y_1 = 0, \quad Y_p = \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, p-1), \quad 2 \leq p \leq d(n-1) + 1.$$

By Theorem 3.1, we have the result

$$N(K_n^d, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{d(n-1)+1} N(K_p, k) Y_p,$$

where

$$Y_1 = 0, Y_p = \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, p-1), \quad 2 \leq p \leq d(n-1)+1,$$

$d(n-1)+1$ is the number of vertices of K_n^d . \square

Theorem 5.8. *Suppose G is a windgraph K_n^2 , special $d=2$, then*

$$N(K_n^2, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{2n-1} N(K_p, k) \sum_{k=1}^{2n-2} \sum_{l_1+l_2=k} S(n-1, l_1) S(n-1, l_2) s(k, p-1),$$

and $2 \leq k \leq 2n-1$.

Proof. Omitted. \square

Theorem 5.9. *If G is a windgraph K_n^d , K_1 is a meet vertex of K_n with the number d , then*

$$A(K_n^d) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=2}^{d(n-1)+1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!} \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, p-1),$$

where $d(n-1)+1$ is the number of vertices of K_n^d .

Proof. Because G is a windgraph K_n^d , and the number of vertices is $d(n-1)+1$, by Theorem 5.7, then the chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} is

$$f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{r=1}^{d(n-1)} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, r) \right\} t^{r+1}.$$

We have coefficients of $f(\bar{G}, t)$ are

$$Y_1 = 0, Y_p = \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, p-1), \quad 2 \leq p \leq d(n-1)+1,$$

By Theorem 4.1,

$$A(K_n^d) = \sum_{p=1}^{d(n-1)+1} A(K_p) Y_p$$

and by Lemma 2.2

$$A(K_p) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!}, \quad 2 \leq p \leq n,$$

namely,

$$A(K_n^d) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=2}^{d(n-1)+1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!} Y_p,$$

then we have the result

$$A(K_n^d) = \frac{1}{e} \sum_{p=2}^{d(n-1)+1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{k^p}{k!} \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)} \left[\sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n-1, l_i) \right] s(k, p-1),$$

where $d(n-1)+1$ is the number of vertices of K_n^d . So far, we have gained the explicit formulas of classes of graphs on enumeration of $S^{(n)}$ -factors. \square

6. Combinatorial identities for $N(G, k)$

Theorem 6.1. *If $N(K_p, k)$ is the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly k components in K_p , and $n \in N$, $1 \leq p, k \leq n$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} N(K_p, k) \times \\ & \sum_{0 \leq h \leq k-r} (-1)^h \binom{k-1+h}{k-r+h} \binom{2k-r}{k-r-h} N(K_{k-r+h}, h) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $f(G, t)$ be the chromatic polynomial of G . Then

$$\begin{aligned} f(G, t) &= \sum_{r=1}^n \left[\sum_{k=1}^n N(\bar{G}, k) \times \right. & (6.1) \\ & \left. \sum_{0 \leq h \leq k-r} (-1)^h \binom{k-1+h}{k-r+h} \binom{2k-r}{k-r-h} N(K_{k-r+h}, h) \right] t^r \quad (\text{see [7]}), \end{aligned}$$

where K_{k-r+h} is a complete graph with $k-r+h$ vertices. When $t=1$, then

$$f(G, 1) = \sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n N(\bar{G}, k) \sum_{0 \leq h \leq k-r} (-1)^h \binom{k-1+h}{k-r+h} \binom{2k-r}{k-r-h} N(K_{k-r+h}, h).$$

On the other hand, if G is not an empty graph, let $t=1$, then $f(G, 1)=0$. So G is not an empty graph

$$\sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n N(\bar{G}, k) \sum_{0 \leq h \leq k-r} (-1)^h \binom{k-1+h}{k-r+h} \binom{2k-r}{k-r-h} N(K_{k-r+h}, h) = 0.$$

Suppose G is a tree T with n vertices, and by Theorem 5.5, then we have

$$N(\bar{G}, k) = \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} N(K_p, k).$$

Finally, there exists a combinatorial identity for $N(K_p, k)$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \sum_{p=k}^n (-1)^{n-p} \binom{n-1}{p-1} N(K_p, k) \times & (6.2) \\ & \sum_{0 \leq h \leq k-r} (-1)^h \binom{k-1+h}{k-r+h} \binom{2k-r}{k-r-h} N(K_{k-r+h}, h) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\substack{\sum_{i=1}^p ib_i=p, \\ \sum_{i=1}^p b_i=k}} \frac{p!}{b_1!} \prod_{i \geq 2} \frac{1}{b_i!(i!)^{b_i}}, \quad 1 \leq p, k \leq n.$$

□

Theorem 6.2. *If $S(n, k)$ is the Stirling number of the second kind, $s(k, r)$ is the Stirling number of the first kind, then there exists a combinatorial identity*

$$\sum_{r=1}^{dn} \sum_{k=1}^{dn} \sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n, l_i) s(k, r) = 0.$$

Proof. Let G be a complete d -partite graph, $G = K_{n,n,\dots,n}$ with with the number d of n , dn is the number of vertices of G ,

$$N(\bar{G}, k) = \sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} N(K_n, l_1) N(K_n, l_2) \cdots N(K_n, l_d).$$

By Lemma 2.4,

$$N(\bar{G}, k) = \sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} S(n, l_1) S(n, l_2) \cdots S(n, l_d).$$

By Lemma 2.6, then there exists combinatorial identity as follows:

$$\sum_{r=1}^{dn} \sum_{k=1}^{dn} \sum_{l_1+\dots+l_d=k} \prod_{i=1}^d S(n, l_i) s(k, r) = 0.$$

□

Corollary 6.3. *There exists a combinatorial identity*

$$\sum_{r=1}^{2n} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \sum_{l_1+l_2=k} S(n, l_1) S(n, l_2) s(k, r) = 0,$$

where $S(n, k)$ is the Stirling number of the second kind, $s(k, r)$ is the Stirling number of the first kind.

Proof. Let G be a complete 2-partite graph $G = K_{n,n}$. Then

$$N(\bar{G}, k) = \sum_{l_1+l_2=k} S(n, l_1) S(n, l_2).$$

By Theorem 6.2, the proof is proved. □

7. The Counting formula of K_d -factors in any complete d -partite graph

In the section, we give the explicit formula of enumeration of K_d -factors in any complete d -partite graph. It is a very difficult and value problem that so far these problems of factors have been researched, involving 1-factors, (g,f)-factors and $S^{(n)}$ -factors.

Theorem 7.1. *Suppose G is a complete d -partite graph $G = K_{n,n,\dots,n}$ with dn vertices, then the explicit formula of the number of all K_d -factors in G is as follows:*

$$N(G, n) = \sum_{p=n}^{dn} N(K_p, n) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n, l_j).$$

Proof. If $G = K_{n,n,\dots,n}$ is a complete d -partite graph, then $\bar{G} = K_n \cup K_n \cup \dots \cup K_n$, any $p, q, p = q = n, K_p \cap K_q = \phi$. The chromatic polynomial of \bar{G} is

$$\begin{aligned} f(\bar{G}, t) &= f(K_n, t) \cdot f(K_n, t) \cdots f(K_n, t) \\ f(\bar{G}, t) &= \prod_{k=1}^n (t - k + 1) \prod_{k=1}^n (t - k + 1) \cdots \prod_{k=1}^n (t - k + 1) \\ &= \sum_{l_1=0}^n s(n, l_1) t^{l_1} \sum_{l_2=0}^n s(n, l_2) t^{l_2} \cdots \sum_{l_d=0}^n s(n, l_d) t^{l_d} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^{dn} \left[\sum_{l_1+l_2+\dots+l_d=r} s(n, l_1) s(n, l_2) \cdots s(n, l_d) \right] t^r, \end{aligned}$$

then

$$Y_p = \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n, l_j), 1 \leq p \leq dn,$$

where $n + n + \dots + n = dn$. By Theorem 3.1, then the number of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly k components in any complete d -partite graph $K_{n,n,\dots,n}$

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{dn} N(K_p, k) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n, l_j).$$

K_k -factor is a special case of $S^{(n)}$ -factor. Because G is a complete d -partite graph, then G is the graph without K_{d+1} subgraphs.

Each component of $S^{(dn)}$ -factors with exactly n components in G is all isomorphic to K_d . So that $N(G, n)$ is equal to the number of all K_d -factors in G . Finally, we gain the explicit formula of all K_d -factors in any complete d -partite graph as follows:

$$N(G, n) = \sum_{p=n}^{dn} N(K_p, n) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n, l_j).$$

□

Corollary 7.2. *If G is a complete 3-partite graph $K_{n,n,n}$, then the number of all K_3 -factors in any complete 3-partite graph is as follows:*

$$\sum_{p=n}^{3n} N(K_p, n) = \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

Proof. Let $d = 3$. Then by Theorem 7.1 we gain the number of all K_3 -factors in any complete 3-partite graph is as follows:

$$\sum_{p=n}^{3n} N(K_p, n) = \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

□

Corollary 7.3. *If G is a complete 3-partite graph $K_{n,n,n}$, then there exists the combinatorial identity*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{3n} k! N(G, k) \binom{3n}{k} = (n!)^3 \binom{3n}{2n, n}^3,$$

where

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{3n} N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

Proof. If $G = (X_1, X_2, X_3)$ is a complete 3-partite graph, $|X_1| = |X_2| = |X_3| = n$, namely $K_{n,n,n}$, then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{3n} k! N(G, k) \binom{3n}{k} = (n!)^3 \binom{3n}{2n, n}^3.$$

(see LiMin Yang and TianMing Wang[12]). By the proving course of Theorem 7.1, we obtain the formula

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{dn} N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n, l_j).$$

Let $d = 3$. Then we derive the combinatorial identity

$$\sum_{k=1}^{3n} k! N(G, k) \binom{3n}{k} = (n!)^3 \binom{3n}{2n, n}^3,$$

where

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{3n} N(K_p, k) = \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

□

Corollary 7.4. *If G is a complete 2-partite graph $K_{n,n}$, then there exists the combinatorial identity*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} k!N(G, k) \binom{2n}{k} = (n!)^2 \binom{2n}{n, n},$$

where

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{2n} N(K_p, k) \sum_{l_1+l_2=p} s(n, l_1)s(n, l_2)$$

Proof. If $G = (X_1, X_2)$ is a complete 2-partite graph, $|X_1| = |X_2| = n$, namely $K_{n,n}$, then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} k!N(G, k) \binom{2n}{k} = (n!)^2 \binom{2n}{n, n}.$$

(see LiMin Yang and TianMing Wang[12]). By the proving course of Theorem 7.1,

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{2n} N(K_p, k) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n, l_j).$$

Let $d = 2$. Then we give the combinatorial identity

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} k!N(G, k) \binom{2n}{k} = (n!)^2 \binom{2n}{n, n},$$

where

$$N(G, k) = \sum_{p=k}^{2n} N(K_p, k) \sum_{l_1+l_2=p} s(n, l_1)s(n, l_2)$$

□

Here we will give the counting theorem of K_l -factors in G without any K_{l+1} subgraph (or K_{l+1} -free graphs).

Theorem 7.5. *If G is a graph without any K_{l+1} subgraph (or K_{l+1} -free graphs) and has n vertices, and the chromatic polynomial of the complementary graph \bar{G} of G is $f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{p=1}^n Y_p t^p$, then the number of all K_l -factors with exactly m components is the following*

$$N(G, m) = \sum_{p=m}^n N(K_p, m) Y_p,$$

where $n = ml$.

Proof. Because G is the graph without any K_{l+1} subgraph, Each component of S^n -factors with exactly m components in G is all isomorphic to K_l , and $n = ml$, so that $N(G, m)$ is equal to the number of all K_l -factors in G . By Theorem 3.1, then

$$N(G, m) = \sum_{p=m}^n N(K_p, m) Y_p,$$

where $n = ml$. □

8. The counting formula of the number of covers on shortest circles

C_n is a longest circle in any graph G , C_3 is a shortest circle in any graph G , and $K_3 = C_3$.

Definition 8.1. If M is a spanning subgraph of the graph G , each component of M is all isomorphic to C_3 , then M is called one cover of shortest circles.

Let $\Omega(G)$ denote the number of all covers of shortest circles.

Theorem 8.2. If G is a complete 3-partite graph $K_{n,n,n}$, then the number all covers on shortest circles in any complete 3-partite graph is as follows:

$$\Omega(G) = \sum_{p=n}^{3n} N(K_p, n) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

Proof. Let $d = 3$. Then by Theorem 7.1 we gain the number of all K_3 -factors in any complete 3-partite graph is as follows:

$$\sum_{p=n}^{3n} N(K_p, n) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

Because of $K_3 = C_3$, then $\Omega(G)$ is equal to the number of all K_3 -factors in any complete 3-partite graph G . So that by using of enumeration of $S^{(n)}$ -factors, we solve the counting formula of the number of covers on shortest circles as follows:

$$\Omega(G) = \sum_{p=n}^{3n} N(K_p, n) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq 3} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^3 s(n, l_j).$$

Here we will give the counting theorem of the number of all covers of shortest circles in any graph G without K_4 subgraphs (or K_4 -free graph). □

Theorem 8.3. If G is a graph without K_4 subgraphs (or K_4 -free graph) and has n vertices, and the chromatic polynomial of the complementary graph \bar{G} of G is $f(\bar{G}, t) = \sum_{p=1}^n Y_p t^p$, then the number of all covers of shortest circles is as follows:

$$\Omega(G) = \sum_{p=m}^{3m} N(K_p, m) Y_p,$$

where $n = 3m$.

Proof. Because G is the graph without K_4 subgraphs, each component of $S^{(n)}$ -factors with exactly m components in G is all isomorphic to K_3 , and $n = 3m$, so that $N(G, m)$ is equal to the number of all K_3 -factors in G . By Theorem 3.1, then

$$N(G, m) = \sum_{p=m}^{3m} N(K_p, m) Y_p,$$

where $n = 3m$. On the other hand $K_3 = C_3$, the number of all covers of shortest circles is equal to the number of all K_3 -factors in G without any K_4 subgraph. Then

$$\Omega(G) = N(G, m).$$

Finally, we derive the counting formula of the number of covers on shortest circles in G without any K_4 subgraph

$$\Omega(G) = \sum_{p=m}^{3m} N(K_p, m) Y_p,$$

where $n = 3m$. □

9. The mean color number of any windgraph K_n^d

Definition 9.1. For any n -coloring Γ of G , let $L(\Gamma)$ denote the actual number of colors used, the average of $L(\Gamma)^s$ over all n -coloring Γ is called the mean color number.

Let $\mu(G)$ denote the mean colour number of any graph.

Theorem 9.2. If $\mu(G)$ is the mean colour number of any windgraph K_n^d , and

$$H(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)+1} (d(n-1)+1)_k \sum_{p=k-1}^{d(n-1)} N(K_p, k-1) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n-1, l_j) t^k,$$

then the explicit formula

$$\mu(K_n^d) = \frac{H'(1)}{H(1)}.$$

Proof. If $\mu(G)$ is the mean colour number of any windgraph K_n^d , then $\bar{G} = K_1 \cup H$ and $K_1 \cap H = \phi$, H is a complete d -partite graph, let $H = K_{n-1, n-1, \dots, n-1}$, the number of $n-1$ is d , we have the formula

$$N(\bar{G}, k) = \sum_{l+m=k} N(K_1, l) N(H, m) = N(H, k-1).$$

By the proving course of Theorem 7.1, we gain

$$N(H, k-1) = \sum_{p=k-1}^{d(n-1)} N(K_p, k-1) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n-1, l_j).$$

If $\mu(G)$ is the mean colour number of any graph with n vertices G , and

$$H(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n (n)_k N(\bar{G}, k) t^k,$$

then

$$\mu(G) = \frac{H'(1)}{H(1)}.$$

(see Yang and Wang[17],2004).Here we have solved the counting formula of $N(\bar{G}, k)$ by the representing formula of $N(G, k)$. Finally, we derive the explicit formula

$$\mu(K_n^d) = \frac{H'(1)}{H(1)},$$

where

$$H(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{d(n-1)+1} (d(n-1) + 1)_k \sum_{p=k-1}^{d(n-1)} N(K_p, k-1) \sum_{\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} l_j = p} \prod_{j=1}^d s(n-1, l_j) t^k .$$

For any windgraph graph,by means of methods of Bartels and Welsh(1995)

(see[18]), and F.M.Dong(2003)(see[19]),we can't gain the explicit formula. By the representing formula of $N(G, k)$, we gain a new way to obtain the explicit formulas on the mean color numbers. \square

10. Conclusions and future work

In this paper, our main problems are the representing formula of $N(G, k)$ and the counting formula of K_d -factors in any complete d -partite graph $K_{n,n,\dots,n}$,we have solved the representing formula of $N(G, k)$ and the counting formula of complete d -partite graph.We present classes of graphs counting formulas for $N(G, k)$ and $A(G)$, specially, gain the explicit formula of $N(\bar{T}, k)$ of the complementary \bar{T} of any tree T , and derive some new combinatorial identities.Finally, we solve the counting formula of the number of covers on shortest circles.The representing formula of $N(G, k)$ has be cited in Yang and Wang [16] and [17],2004,India.We have cited the representing formula of $N(G, k)$,Reviewer Cédric Lamthe ,2005.In future work,the representing formula of $N(G, k)$ will be cited again by us in our papers, we will solve independent set polynomials $I(G, x)$.

Independent set polynomials $I(G, x)$ are defined as

$$I(G, x) = \sum_{k=1}^n b_k(G) x^k = \sum_{I \subset v(G)} \prod_{v \in I} x,$$

where let $b_k(G)$ be exactly k -independent sets of G .

Complexity: It is easy to see that $I(G, x)$ is NP-hard to compute.(see [21]).

The representing formula of $N(G, k)$ will be gained deep applications in future research.

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